
**ATTITUDE OF PARENTS TOWARDS GIRL'S EDUCATION IN THE
DISTRICT OF UTTAR DINAJPUR**

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Abstract:

The 21st centuries growth in various sectors has led our country towards achieving the distinction of one of the growing nations in the world. Various efforts have been made by the Government as well as Non-Government Organizations but the literacy rate is increased if we compare it with the few decades back, but the 100 percent literacy is not achieved till today. The literacy rate of the disadvantaged community is still poor. The objectives of the study are to examine the attitudes of Scheduled caste parents towards education of their girl child in relation to locale (rural & urban) variation, type of family (Joint & Nuclear) variation, above graduate Scheduled caste parents and below graduate scheduled caste parents. Descriptive method is selected for study. The findings of the study are that there is significant difference of Scheduled caste Parents' attitude towards girls' education in relation to locale (rural & urban) variation, type of family (Joint & Nuclear) variation and education variation.

Key Words: Attitude, Girls' Education, Scheduled caste parents, Locale

1.0. Introduction

In West Bengal, in spite of the various constitutional safeguards and all the different schemes by the state government, literacy level of the rural and disadvantaged mass is found to be much lower than that of the rest of the society. This may cause by the various factors. Among these factors, socio-economic statuses, parental attitude, their interest to give education to their girl children, their awareness regarding education and so on play a vital role. While parents of the disadvantaged girl children are not highly in favour of schooling and education of their girl children, today's scenario might have improved with widespread awareness regarding value of education. In this context, it is imperative to evaluate the perceptions and attitude of these parents.

Parents' positive attitude towards girl child's education is important in determining school attendance and academic achievement of the child. Favourable attitude towards schooling and education enhances parental involvement in girl children's present and future studies. Parent's attitude towards their girl children's education is affected adversely by low socio-economic status and since the tribal constitute the disadvantaged population, it is expected that the attitude of parents of tribal girl children will be unfavourable towards education. However, the present study aims to examine whether the parents of rural and urban area, today, exhibit a positive and favorable attitude towards their girl children's education as a result of increasing awareness of values of education through Government Endeavour's and initiatives. Parental attitude is a measure or an index of parental involvement. A child, brought up with affection and care in the least restrictive environment would be able to cope up better with the sighted world. Therefore, the family shapes the social integration of the child more than a formal school. Turnbull (1983) has identified four basic parental roles- parents as educational decision makers; parents as parents; parents as teachers and parents as advocates. Since the parent's attitude is so important,

it is essential that the home and school work closely together, especially for children with disabilities. The Warnock Report (1978) stresses the importance of parents being partners in the education of their children. The role of parents should actively support and enrich the educational processes. Korth (1981) states that parents should be recognized as the major teacher of their children and the professional should be considered consultants to parents. Tait (1972) opines that the parents' psychological well-being and the ease or difficulties with which they decipher the cues that facilitate the socialization process influence the personal and social development of the child. It is the parents who exert the major influence on the development of the child from birth to maturity. One of the most important attributes of parental attitude is consistency. As children mature into adolescence, family involvement in their learning remains important. Family involvement practices at home and at school have been found to influence secondary school students' academic achievement, school attendance, and graduation and college matriculation rates (Dornbusch & Ritter, 1988; Plank & Jordan, 1997). Despite its importance, however, families' active involvement in their girl children's education declines as they progress from elementary school to middle and high school (Dauber & Epstein, 1993; Lee, 1994). Research suggests that schools can reverse the decline in parent involvement by developing comprehensive programs of partnership (Eccles & Harold, 1993; Epstein & Connors, 1994). Previous research shows that family involvement helps for achieving higher attendance, better grade point averages and lower dropout rates.

Even if India has a long and rich heritage of education in both pre and post-independence era, education of the minority communities has remained a sensitive issue. Under the Buddhist influence, education was available to virtually everyone who wanted it. During 11th century, the Scheduled castes established elementary and secondary schools, Madrasas or colleges and universities.

1.2. Reviews of related literature

TNS Social research (September 2003-June 2004) stated that parents' attitudes towards education were generally very positive. The majority (97%) agreed that a good education would help their child to get ahead in life. While 93% thought the qualifications were important to their child's future, 90% also agreed that children learn important life skills at school. Three quarters of parents (76%) agreed that their child's school is good at communicating with them and the majority (86%) agreed that their child's teachers do a great job. Just over a fifth (22%) felt that their child's school tended to be too interested in bright children at the expense of the others, although only 7% thought that the school takes too much interest in their child's home life. Just under a fifth of parents/carers (18%) thought that most of the things their child learns at school are not relevant to real life. A small proportion (14%) of parents saw it as acceptable that if their child did not want to study now, s/he could study when s/he was older. Their study was based on to identify whether there were any differences in parents' attitudes towards attendance between the general population and a group of parents whose children were currently not attending school. This research has not identified any differences in the attitudes of parents in the general population. Research indicates that most parents show considerable interest in their child's school, and this is equally the case for parents of children who have attendance problems. In an Ofsted report (2001) on attendance and behaviour in secondary schools, it has been found (O'Keefe, 1993) that most schools usually enjoyed good working relationships with parents. In fact, most of the parents/carers said they wanted more contact with schools. The majority of parents were appreciative of the concern and time given by head teachers and staff, even when approached about issues concerning their children's attendance or behaviour. However, it was also found that a small proportion of parents/carers were very uncooperative with the schools, and their attitudes, whether confrontational or passive, served to reinforce their children's negative attitude towards school.

1.3. Objectives of the Study

The specific objectives are as under:

1. To examine the attitudes of Scheduled caste parents towards education of their girl child.
2. To examine the attitudes of Scheduled caste parents towards education of their girl child in relation to locale (rural & urban) variation.
3. To examine the attitudes of Scheduled caste parents towards education of their girl child in relation to type of family (Joint & Nuclear) variation.
4. To examine the difference between attitude of above graduate Scheduled caste parents and attitude of below graduate scheduled caste parents towards their girl child education.

1.4. Hypothesis of the study

On the basis of the above objectives, the following hypotheses will be formulated:

H1: There is no significant difference of Scheduled caste Parents' attitude towards girls' education.

H2: There is no significant difference of Scheduled caste Parents' attitude towards girls' education in relation to locale (rural & urban) variation.

H3: There is no significant difference of Scheduled caste Parents' attitude towards girls' education in relation to type of family (Joint & Nuclear) variation.

H4: There is no significant difference of Scheduled caste Parents' attitude towards girls' education in relation to education variation.

1.5. Operational definitions of the terms used

Attitude: It's a mental position or emotional feelings about products, services, ideas, issues and institutions. A complex mental state involving beliefs and feelings and values and dispositions to act in certain ways.

Education: The modification of the attitude and behaviour through training in formal learning systems.

1.6. Scope of the Study

Swami Vivekananda had introduced Kumari puja in the Belur math hundred years ago. It was not just a religious ritual. It was actually a message to the society regarding the significance of a girl child. It was a humble gesture toward girls population in the society. So, education of girls and girls is an area of major national concern both as a development imperative and as a human right. Girls are viewed as the most deprived and disadvantaged section of the Indian society. Indian girls and girls have been subjected to various kinds of social discrimination including education. We know that Scheduled caste girls are still lagging behind in the entire sphere and are deprived of all the educational opportunities especially in the state West Bengal. It is a matter of concern for me to analyze the impact of 'Girls education' on empowerment of Scheduled caste girls in West Bengal with special reference to Uttar Dinajpur district.

2.0. Method of the study

For the present study, the descriptive method of research has been used. Descriptive research may be characterized as simply the attempt to determine, describe or identify, what is Descriptive research aims at casting light on current issues or problem through a process of data collection that enables them to describe the situation more completely than was possible without employing this method.

2.1. Research Design

It is a descriptive study which investigates the attitude of Scheduled caste parents towards their girl child education. Block 1 consists of 200 samples and Block 2 consists of 200 samples.

2.2. Population

The study aimed at studying the attitude of Scheduled caste parents towards their girl child education in both rural and urban area of UTTAR DINAJPUR District of West Bengal.

2.3. Sample

Sample were taken from 2 Blocks of UTTAR DINAJPUR district of West Bengal according to their administrative block. A sample of 400 house hold (Parents) were selected by purposive method. The variables of the study are locale (Rural & Urban), Socio-Economic Status (High SES & Low SES), Education (Above graduate and below graduate) and type of family (Joint & Nuclear).

2.4. Sampling technique

For the present study the researcher used Purposive Sampling Technique for data collection.

2.5. Tools used for data collection:

The tools used for this study were:

Scale for measuring parents' attitude towards girls' education (2017) by Kalam, Uzma and Lal, Banwari was used for data collection. There are 25 Statements in this scale. Respondents selected one option out of 5 options such as Strongly disagree, Disagree, Uncertain, Agree and Strongly agree. 16 statements are negative and 9 statements are positive in this scale. Negative statements scoring is 5,4,3,2 and 1. Positive statements scoring is 1,2,3,4 and 5. The reliability of the instrument is 0.87 and validity is content validity.

2.6. Techniques of data collection:

The following techniques have been used for this study:

- Questioning techniques were adopted for collection of data through questionnaires.

- The test of significance of difference ('t') between the means of two contrasting sub-samples was calculated to find out significant difference in two sub samples in relation to locale, education and type of family.

3.0. Results and Discussion

The result has been organized under differential analysis and study of relationship on the variables and between the variables. For determining the significance of differences between the mean of the contrast "t" test was adopted and the value of "t" ratio is presented in the table followed by discussion. The result obtained in the present study was studied in corroboration with other studies.

3.1. Locale variation differences on scheduled caste Parents' attitude towards girls' Education

One of the objectives of the study was to be found out if there exist any locale variation differences on scheduled caste Parents' attitude towards girls' Education, therefore the null hypothesis was stated as "there is no significant difference in scheduled caste Parents' attitude towards girls' Education in relation to locale variation".

In order to find out differences if any of the scores on scheduled caste Parents' attitude towards girls' Education of rural and urban, the test of significance of difference between the means of two sub samples was calculated and tested for significance. The result has been presented in the following table:

Table 1: Summary of test of significance of differences between locale variation on scheduled caste Parents' attitude towards girls' Education

Locale variation	N	Mean	SD	SE _D	't'	Remarks
Rural	200	78.67	32.92	1.52.	2.92	Significan

Urban	200	69.16	23.7	3		t
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Critical value of ‘t’ with df (98) at 0.01=2.63 and 0.05=1.98

The obtained value 2.92 is greater than the tabular value at 0.05 levels 1.98 and at 0.01 level 2.63 so it is significant and the null hypothesis that states there exist no significant difference between rural and urban scheduled caste Parents’ attitude towards girls’ Education in relation to locale variation will be rejected. This finding was in conformity with the findings of Mingat, 2007; Shavit and Blossfeld, 1993; Jencks, 1972; Coleman et al., 1966, Sen, 1992, Caldwell, 1982 and Bauch 1991.

3.2. Type of Family variation differences on scheduled caste Parents’ attitude towards girls’ Education

One of the objectives of the study was to be found out if there exist any type of family variation differences on scheduled caste Parents’ attitude towards girls’ Education, therefore the null hypothesis was stated as “there is no significant difference in scheduled caste Parents’ attitude towards girls’ Education in relation to type of family variation”.

In order to find out differences if any of the scores on scheduled caste Parents’ attitude towards girls’ Education of joint and nuclear family, the test of significance of difference between the means of two sub samples was calculated and tested for significance. The result has been presented in the following table:

Table 2: Summary of test of significance of differences between type of family variation of scheduled caste Parents’ attitude towards girls’ Education

Type of Family variation	N	Mean	S. D	SE _D	‘t’	Remarks
Joint Family	200	56.32	22.13	0.54	3.07	Significant
Nuclear Family	200	62.11	23.34			

Critical value of ‘t’ with df (98) at 0.01=2.63 and 0.05=1.98

The obtained value 3.07 is greater than the tabular value at 0.05 levels 1.98 and at 0.01 level 2.63 so it is significant and the null hypothesis that states there exist no significant difference between scheduled caste Parents’ attitude towards girls’ Education in relation to type of family variation will be rejected. This finding was in conformity with the findings of Dornbusch and Ritter (1988), Bogunović Blanka and Polovina Nada (2007) and Useem (1992).

3.3. Education variation differences on scheduled caste Parents’ attitude towards girls’ Education

One of the objectives of the study was to be found out if there exist any education variation differences on scheduled caste Parents’ attitude towards girls’ Education, therefore the null hypothesis was stated as “there is no significant difference in scheduled caste Parents’ attitude towards girls’ Education in relation to education variation”.

In order to find out differences if any of the scores on scheduled caste Parents’ attitude towards girls’ Education of above graduate and below graduate parents, the test of significance of difference between the means of two sub samples was calculated and tested for significance.

The result has been presented in the following table:

Education variation	N	Mean	S. D	SE _D	‘t’	Remarks
Above Graduate	200	65.37	23.22	1.42	2.92	Significant
Below Graduate	200	76.66	33.45			

Table 3: Summary of test of significance of differences between the education variation of scheduled caste Parents’ attitude towards girls’ Education

Critical value of ‘t’ with d f (98) at 0.01=2.63 and 0.05=1.98

The obtained value 2.92 is greater than the tabular value at 0.05 levels 1.98 and at 0.01 level 2.63 so it is significant and the null hypothesis that states there exist no significant difference between the education variation of scheduled caste Parents' attitude towards girls' Education will be rejected. This finding was in conformity with the findings of Dornbusch and Ritter (1988), Emerson & Portela Souza, 2007, Breen and Goldthorpe, (1997).

4.0. Findings of the Study

After thorough study and data analysis, following findings had been noticed:

1. There is significant difference of Scheduled caste Parents' attitude towards girls' education.
2. There is significant difference of Scheduled caste Parents' attitude towards girls' education in relation to locale (rural & urban) variation.
3. There is significant difference of Scheduled caste Parents' attitude towards girls' education in relation to type of family (Joint & Nuclear) variation.
4. There is significant difference of Scheduled caste Parents' attitude towards girls' education in relation to education variation.

4.1. The Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made;

- i. The government should empower parents who are handicapped by poverty in order to enable have capital to purchase instructional material for their children.
- ii. The government should carry out a sensitization and public awareness programs in order bring parent awareness on the benefits of girl-child education in the society.
- iii. The government should also make parents to be aware that educating the girl-child does diminish the cultural value rather it promotes civilization.
- iv. The religious leaders should also make parents be aware of the importance of educating girls.

v. The mass education and new consciousness will refine our personal beliefs and traditional system which are barriers to social progress. We should encourage the education of the women in all its ramifications in country. We need people both males and females who can lead to tumultuous ship to the safety. And probably, if we induce the training of our daughters, they could display their ingenuity to partake and calm the trouble sea.

4.2. Implications for further research

The present study opens up certain avenues for further research, which are:

- The present study can be replicated in different parts of the country with large sample and with various groups.
- The present study can be replicated on a large and more representative sample, so that the result obtained may be more reliable.
- Similar studies can be conducted on the other stakeholders of education to measure their attitude towards girls' education.
- The study of the same nature can be undertaken for the different states of the country.

4.3. Conclusion

Discrimination as a concept as old as time itself, it is a natural phenomenon so it is difficult and sometimes improper to totally eradicate it in society. But effects should be geared to minimize and abridge its adverse effect in society in order to achieve harmonious co-existence. Every society on the earth imbibes this conception whatever it does either in the family cycle, the village cycle or the state cycle. It also gives a challenge to those discriminated against. There are five factors militating against the female children compulsory education. Though, the fourth factor is particularly partly attributed to both the parents and the daughters themselves. The traditional Cum-cultural factor maintains the parents' prerogative as divine, no culture or tradition can

survive if it is automatically affected by social exchange. The parents are likely to send their daughters to schools. It such ideas did not infringe the laid down traditions and custom of the society. The society will not tolerate the violation of its established beliefs and the word of God as prophesized by the Holy prophet and elders by sending the female children of the believers to schools. It is religious that caters for the children are moral and spiritual uplifted.

5.0. References

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